

1 **Dynamic TOX gene expression in solid tumors of humans with lung cancer and breast cancer.**

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6 Tox factors function in the nucleus to establish exhaustion program features in the immune system and are
7 targets of the senescence program in transformation of non-hematopoietic cells resulting in solid tumors.
8 We observed significant silencing of TOX2 during transformation of the lung in non-small cell lung cancer.
9 In luminal B breast cancer, TOX3 was instead activated during the course of transformation; in the luminal
10 A subtype, TOX4 was activated instead. We describe subtype and tissue specific modulation of TOX
11 family during transformation in humans.

12 **References**

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